

ENIGMA: A Scalable Simulator for IoT and Edge Computing

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Abstract—In recent years, the devices that make up the Internet of Things (IoT) paradigm have been increasing in number and complexity as different layers of network computing, such as Cloud, Edge and Fog Computing, have emerged. Thanks to these latest paradigms and their different types of communications, it has been possible to reduce and distribute the computational load on the network. However, to build these infrastructures and reduce the cost, it is necessary to use a simulation platform to model these environments and analyze their behavior (power consumption, CPU usage, bandwidth, etc.) beforehand. An essential aspect of simulators is scalability, the ability to add new components and simulate large infrastructures without compromising the performance of the simulator. Many existing simulators, as will be discussed in this article, cannot scale adequately as new elements are added to the system. Furthermore, in these environments, it is useful to simulate mobile devices and to know the location of these devices for the development and analysis of new algorithms. To solve these problems, this article presents and describes the ENIGMA simulator. ENIGMA is a scalable simulator of Edge, Fog and Cloud computing infrastructures, which allows to efficiently simulate a large number of devices and elements and to analyze different characteristics (CPU usage, power consumption, network bandwidth, application execution time, etc.). Its objective is to analyze new infrastructures and algorithms. ENIGMA also includes support for including mobile devices and an API to integrate their visualization in graphical maps. The article presents an evaluation to compare the scalability of ENIGMA with other state-of-the-art simulators and different use cases that illustrate its operation.

Index Terms—Internet of Things, Simulation, Fog and Cloud Computing, Mobility, Scalability

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, computing and information storage have been moved to the cloud, using paradigms that allow managing the data that users generate daily. In addition, the reduction in the cost of smart devices has led to new challenges and the need to create new infrastructures capable of managing the data they generate [1].

The proliferation of these devices and new types of services and applications led to the emergence of the Internet of Things (IoT) [2] paradigm and the consequent challenges to being

able to read, store or even process the immense amount of information that all these devices use or generate continuously.

Initially, there were no paradigms that could process all this information, exceeding the capacities and bandwidth available on the network. For these reasons, paradigms such as Cloud Computing [3] [4], Edge Computing [5], Fog Computing [6] [7] or Mobile Edge Computing [8] emerged. Firstly, Cloud Computing was used as a measure to solve these problems, taking computing to the cloud and thus allowing the distribution of information among the different servers that make up the infrastructure to reduce congestion and speed up data processing.

However, designing these infrastructures may not be practical and, in addition, generating testbeds for this type of scenario can involve very high costs as there are many devices and connections involved. For these reasons, prior studies must be carried out to analyze the feasibility of the infrastructure and the desired scenarios. This is why the solution chosen worldwide is based on the use of simulators that make it possible to define an environment by introducing the desired scenarios, applications, or devices and obtain results that make it possible to decide whether or not it is feasible to implement (such as bandwidth or CPU usage).

Therefore, this work presents the development of a simulator called ENIGMA (gEneric Iot edGe siMULator) [9], based on the SimGrid [10] simulation tool, capable of simulating Edge and Fog Computing environments that facilitate the user the study and analysis of scenarios or Cloud environments, allowing the specification of different characteristics of the components (CPU, RAM, bandwidth, power consumption, etc.), the analysis of different types of applications and even the study of environments that include the mobility of sensors or mobile devices. This will allow users to easily create environments, allowing them to define the components and connections available to them. In addition, building these infrastructures without prior knowledge is usually not easy, and generating test benches for certain scenarios involves

high costs, so using simulators capable of performing these tasks speeds up and lowers the costs of implementing such infrastructures.

In addition, there are not a large number of simulators capable of providing mobility in sensors or devices [11], so it becomes complicated to determine a good configuration to study the infrastructure. That is why, in addition, we present an extension to SimGrid [10], which is a set of tools for the simulation of large-scale distributed computational systems, where a set of capabilities for component mobility is added. These mobility capabilities provide SimGrid with several features that facilitate the execution of simulations for multiple infrastructures and applications. In addition, this extension to the simulator has been designed as an API of functions that are not restricted to a specific subset of infrastructures, which adds versatility to its use.

II. ENIGMA

ENIGMA¹ (gENERic Iot edGe siMulAtoR) [9] is an Edge and Fog Computing simulator that has been developed by the authors with the aim of performing simulations of this type of infrastructure for the collection of data, such as CPU consumption or energy consumption. The use of this simulator helps to obtain essential information in order to select an environment that satisfies the user's needs.

Fig. 1: ENIGMA Architecture

ENIGMA uses the SimGrid tool as a base, offering the possibility of sending data packets between the components as tasks to be processed during the simulation. SimGrid has been used for ENIGMA because it adds two layers of complexity, one for those who do not know or do not wish to know the internal details of the simulator, thus facilitating its use and reducing its complexity, and another layer for those who want to go deeper into the simulations and infrastructures, allowing to modify and add more elements to the simulation.

As shown in Figure 1, ENIGMA uses all the tools and layers offered by SimGrid for the creation, communication, and information processing of each entity used in the simulation.

First, there are two groups, the client part, formed by the IoT elements, followed by the server part, formed by Fog, Edge, and Cloud components. All these components communicate thanks to the connections that SimGrid allows to create.

For each element that can be configured in the platform, there is a series of parameters that the user will have to define for the correct operation of the simulation. These include the number of elements per group of components, the processor speed in FLOPS (Floating point Operations Per Second), the number of cores, or the latency and bandwidth of the elements. In addition, if you want to analyze the energy consumed, you can add the watts consumed by each component.

As with the developed API, the user will have to define the links of the platform and the components that connect the ends of each link, as well as the latency and bandwidth of the link. The simulator also allows simulating mobile devices and integrating their location and visualization in graphic maps.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. Gantz and D. Reinsel, “The digital universe in 2020: Big data, bigger digital shadows, and biggest growth in the far east,” *IDC iView: IDC Analyze the future*, vol. 2007, no. 2012, pp. 1–16, 2012.
- [2] C. A. Medina, M. R. Pérez, and L. C. Trujillo, “IoT paradigm into the smart city vision: A survey,” in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Internet of Things (iThings) and IEEE Green Computing and Communications (GreenCom) and IEEE Cyber, Physical and Social Computing (CPSCom) and IEEE Smart Data (SmartData)*, 2017, pp. 695–704.
- [3] R. D. Caytiles, S. Lee, and B. Park, “Cloud computing: The next computing paradigm.”
- [4] S. Alonso-Monsalve, F. García-Carballeira, and A. Calderón, “A heterogeneous mobile cloud computing model for hybrid clouds,” *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 87, pp. 651–666, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167739X17313894>
- [5] B. Varghese, N. Wang, S. Barbhuiya, P. Kilpatrick, and D. S. Nikolopoulos, “Challenges and opportunities in edge computing,” in *2016 IEEE International Conference on Smart Cloud (SmartCloud)*, 2016, pp. 20–26.
- [6] S. Chen, T. Zhang, and W. Shi, “Fog computing,” *IEEE Internet Computing*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 4–6, 2017.
- [7] S. Alonso-Monsalve, F. García-Carballeira, and A. Calderón, “Fog computing through public-resource computing and storage,” in *2017 Second International Conference on Fog and Mobile Edge Computing (FMEC)*, 2017, pp. 81–87.
- [8] Y. Yu, “Mobile edge computing towards 5g: Vision, recent progress, and open challenges,” *China Communications*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 89–99, 2016.
- [9] E. Del-Pozo-Puñal and F. García Carballeira, “A generic simulator for edge computing platforms,” in *HPCS2020*, 2020.
- [10] H. Casanova, A. Giersch, A. Legrand, M. Quinson, and F. Suter, “Versatile, scalable, and accurate simulation of distributed applications and platforms,” *Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing*, vol. 74, no. 10, pp. 2899–2917, Jun. 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://hal.inria.fr/hal-01017319>
- [11] S. M. Ghaleb, S. Subramaniam, Z. A. Zukarnain, and A. Muhammed, “Mobility management for iot: a survey,” *EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking*, vol. 2016, no. 1, pp. 1–25, 2016.

¹Available at: <https://github.com/ENIGMA-Sim/ENIGMA>